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Infrastructure-based Perception with Cameras and Radars for Cooperative Driving Scenarios

Alexander Tsaregorodtsev¹, Michael Buchholz¹, and Vasileios Belagiannis²

Abstract—Roadside infrastructure has enjoyed widespread adoption for various tasks such as traffic surveillance, traffic monitoring, control of traffic flow, and prioritization of public transit and emergency vehicles. As automated driving functions and vehicle communications continue to be researched, cooperative and connected driving scenarios can now be realized. Cooperative driving, however, imposes stringent environmental perception and model requirements. In particular, road users, including pedestrians and cyclists, must be reliably detected and accurately localized. Furthermore, the perception framework must have low latency to provide up-to-date information. In this work, we present a refined, camera-based reference point detector design that does not rely on annotated infrastructure datasets and incorporates fusion with cost-effective radar sensor data to increase system reliability, if available. The reference point detector design is realized with box and instance segmentation object detector models to extract object ground points. In parallel, objects are extracted from radar target data through a clustering pipeline and fused with camera object detections. To demonstrate the real-world applicability of our approaches for cooperative driving scenarios, we provide an extensive evaluation of data from a real test site.

I. INTRODUCTION

Roadside infrastructure units (RSUs) have become a vital component of many road networks around the world and an active topic of research [1], [2], mainly due to the widespread availability of inexpensive camera sensors. Early utilization of roadside infrastructure included poles and gantries equipped with camera sensors, which are used to monitor the traffic on the observed road. With the addition of different sensor types, the emergence of vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, and intelligent traffic lights and signage, more applications can be explored. These applications include traffic flow control, traffic warnings and congestion detection, traffic rule enforcement, road condition detection, obstacle and construction site warnings, and prioritization of public transport and emergency vehicles. At the same time, with the increasing availability of automated driving functions, trajectory prediction [3] and cooperative maneuver planning can now be realized, especially with assistance from RSUs, which is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1. Overview of a cooperative planning scenario. Our goal is to provide reliable detections (red and green circles) to the digital twin with a low latency, which enables the cooperative planner to provide safe and optimized maneuver suggestions (blue/violet lines) as well as trajectory predictions (yellow lines).

Several methods have been proposed in the literature for the perception of roadside infrastructure. One of the earlier approaches using cameras is presented in [4]. The drawbacks of these early methods include their limitation to vehicles and the inability to reliably distinguish between different object classes. A more recent work presented in [5] included the ability to classify and estimate 3D boxes for all traffic participants. However, most published methods do not evaluate their localization accuracy since there is usually no ground truth information in world coordinates in the used datasets. Other approaches like [6] rely on lidar sensors, which are not cost-effective compared to cameras. Also, the latency between taking an image from the camera and receiving the object data at a central instance responsible for creating a digital twin of the observed road is also unavailable since the previously mentioned approaches are often not designed to feed data to digital twins; and thus do not consider the communication latency. Therefore, the usability of such approaches for cooperative driving scenarios is largely unexplored.

We propose a refined and optimized approach for infrastructure camera-based detection of road users in live traffic conditions, specifically designed to provide an external perception source for cooperative driving scenarios. The main component of our method consists of a neural network

object detector based on the well-established YOLO architecture [7], which is trained on the BDD100K dataset [8]. Our approach does not rely on any infrastructure-specific datasets. The camera image is pre-processed to remove lens distortion and enhance contrast. The enhanced image is then sent to the object detection network. The output of the object detection network is associated with previous frames to create object tracks. An object’s reference point and orientation in the world coordinate system can be estimated from the object tracks. This condensed object information can be efficiently sent to downstream modules, i.e., multi-object trackers [9], [10], via cellular or wired network connections to create a digital twin of the observed road network. By replacing the box detection model with an instance segmentation model, additional information can be extracted from the object detections. This allows us to estimate the object’s dimensions. To further improve our approach, measurements from low-cost automotive radar sensors are taken and clustered to extract objects. These objects are combined or fused with objects originating from the camera before sending them to downstream modules. With this addition, we show that our fusion strategy between camera and radar can substantially improve the perception reliability under regular and adverse weather conditions like snow. We recorded data at our test site in Ulm-Lehr, Germany [11] while traversing the intersection with a precisely localized test vehicle. This evaluation data is used to measure our perception pipeline’s localization accuracy and detection rate. By additionally labeling the recorded sequence, a detection rate is measured for each object class. This allows us to evaluate the detection performance of vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians and cyclists, as well as the improvements achieved by camera-radar fusion. Our contribution consists of the following parts:

- We propose an efficient reference point detection method for roadside infrastructure.
- Our approach can be combined with existing object mask-based ground point estimation approaches and does not rely on labeled infrastructure datasets.
- We present a simple but effective approach to radar processing and sensor fusion for improved detection reliability.
- We extensively evaluate real-world data collected during cooperative driving tests for various performance metrics and system latency.

II. RELATED WORK

Camera-based infrastructure perception was previously realized in different ways depending on the desired task. For simple traffic surveillance tasks, before the emergence of deep neural networks, background subtraction [12] was used to detect vehicles [13], which were then lifted into 3D space by exploiting the vanishing points of the camera sensor. Modifications of this approach are described by Dubska et al. [4], where the estimated box corners are projected directly into 3D world space using statistical priors. With the increasing availability of neural networks for object detection, the background subtraction was complemented by

a neural network object detector in [14], which was limited to vehicle detection only.

A refinement approach was proposed in [15], where a 3D box detection of a neural network is unpacked into front/back, top, and side views using homography transforms and then fed into another model to determine the exact vehicle type and refine the box detection. It also showed a refinement method using CNNs to estimate the object orientation, which allowed for an even better 3D box fit. Rezaei et al. [5] proposed a method based on geometric constraints, where a recent satellite image of the observed area is employed to calibrate the cameras and create a bird’s eye view map. Using 2D box detections from the camera image and the satellite map, the objects are lifted into 3D boxes using road features and geometry. Other neural network approaches integrate the 3D box lifting into the network and directly estimate 3D boxes from the image, e.g., [16], [17]. Another algorithm described in [18] lifts the image pixels into a pseudo-lidar point cloud using MonoDepth [19], where 3D boxes can be extracted from.

When lidar sensors are integrated into the infrastructure, 3D object detection models such as CenterPoint [20] can be used to obtain 3D boxes. A broader overview of various 3D object detection methods is presented in [21]. Other approaches include fusing camera, lidar, or radar data in a single network. For camera-lidar fusion specific to roadside infrastructure, InfraDet3D [6] was proposed. Additionally, lidar data can be used to extract depth information from the images [22] for subsequent object localization.

III. METHOD

The following section formulates our problem and goal, presents our method, and describes each part of the proposed processing pipeline in detail.

A. Problem Formulation

Consider a camera image \mathcal{I} taken at time t_1 by a roadside camera sensor as well as optional radar targets $\mathbf{r}_i = [r, \alpha, \theta, v_r]$ measured at time t_r consisting of a radial distance r , azimuth angle α , elevation angle θ , and radial velocity v_r . Our goal is, given \mathcal{I} and optionally \mathbf{r} , to extract a list of objects $\mathbf{o}_j = [x, y, \vartheta, p, c, (l, w)]$ containing the UTM [23] reference point position encoded in x and y , an orientation ϑ defined with respect to the UTM Easting axis, a reference point p , and a class label c . If the algorithm provides the length l or width w , they are optionally included in the object state. In this scenario, the reference point can be either the front/back-left/right corner, the object’s geometric center, or, in the case of the front/back/left/right edge, the center point of the edge. In the case of an edge reference, the dimension of the edge can be encoded as the length or width of the object, depending on the object’s orientation. We assume that the transformation from sensor coordinates to the UTM world coordinate system is available. Specifically for the camera transformation, a ground plane needs to be defined since the transformation of a single pixel without depth information results in a ray in world coordinates, which

can then be intersected with the ground plane to obtain a ground point.

B. Image Pre-Processing and Inference

At the beginning of the processing pipeline, an image is obtained from the camera sensor. Depending on the processing steps performed in the camera sensor, the image pixels may require further processing. This includes color space conversions and image rotations for camera sensors rotated by 90°, as object detectors are usually trained on upright images. Then, Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [24] is applied to boost contrast levels and increase the visual separation between different images. At the end of the image pre-processing, the image is undistorted, given the intrinsic lens calibration with radial and tangential distortion coefficients. The undistortion is crucial to the localization accuracy of our approach as a pinhole camera model is used, which is a linear model if expressed in homogeneous coordinates without normalization. Non-linear lens distortions would result in incorrect transformations from image space to world space and vice versa when using the pinhole model.

After CLAHE and undistortion, the image is provided to a YOLO object detector. In particular, we use the YOLOv5s [25] and YOLOv8s [7] model variants due to their small model size and fast inference times. To achieve a high detection rate out-of-the-box, the BDD100K dataset [8] is used for training the models since it contains bounding box labels for the traffic object classes of our interest for cooperative driving use cases (car, motorcycle, bicycle, pedestrian, bus, truck). Furthermore, our models trained on BDD100K generalize well to new camera perspectives and environments since the dataset was recorded with automated vehicles in the US, but our test site is located in Germany.

In order to compare to existing detection approaches, an instance segmentation network is trained and implemented as an alternative, which outputs the object bounding box, class, and detection confidence, as well as a pixel-wise mask of the object. For this purpose, we use the YOLOv8s-seg model, an extension of the standard YOLOv8s model, and train it on the BDD100K dataset. However, since BDD100K only contains instance mask labels for 1/10th of the dataset, its detection performance severely lags far behind that of the box object detection networks. Therefore, we employ the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [26] to automatically generate instance masks from the already present box labels and train the segmentation network on this autolabeled dataset, which yields better results and is used for the final evaluation.

C. Orientation Estimation

The object’s orientation is estimated after obtaining all object bounding boxes and corresponding class labels. We use the bounding box displacement between two frames to extract a direction vector. It should be noted that using this method, the orientation of reversing and parked vehicles cannot be estimated correctly. Objects between two frames must

first be associated to calculate the bounding box displacement. This is done by buffering all object detections from the previous frame and creating an association cost matrix for each possible association. The optimal associations can be determined by applying the Hungarian Algorithm [27]. As the association cost, the inverted DIOU metric [28] between two bounding boxes is used since it additionally penalizes differences in bounding box size and position. Furthermore, if the DIOU is zero, then the cost is set to an arbitrarily high value to prevent association. For this reason, for this approach to work, the time between two frames needs to be short enough such that the bounding box detection of a vehicle obeying the speed limit overlaps between frames.

After associating the objects, a bounding box displacement vector \mathbf{d} can be computed. We define \mathbf{d} as the difference between the center points of the bottom box edges. This is done in order to minimize the direction vector’s projection error since the transformation of a direction vector from image space to world space depends on its origin. Thus, if the transformation is performed from the image plane to the ground plane, and the bottom box edge is assumed to be at least partially contained in the ground plane, it can provide the best vector origin.

When using \mathbf{d} to calculate the object orientation, the resulting value may still be noisy, especially if one of the bounding box sizes was not predicted correctly due to occlusion or previously unseen features. We, thus, smooth the orientation by considering the current and previous displacement values \mathbf{d}_i as:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \arctan2\left(\sum_{i=1}^{\gamma} \beta^i \mathbf{d}_i\right), \quad (1)$$

where we set $\beta = 0.9$ and $\gamma = 3$ to calculate the object orientation $\hat{\alpha}$ in image space.

Using associated bounding boxes and their history, the orientation of stopping and standing vehicles can still be estimated if the object has previously moved. In this case, if the object displacement between two frames falls below a certain threshold, the object is considered static, and its orientation from previous timestamps is reused. A statistical prior is used to provide object orientations for static objects during the pipeline startup, similar to related work. In our case, specifically for cars, we take the bounding box width transformed into world coordinates to determine the most likely orientation of the object since the width of a vehicle usually does not exceed 2.5 m. In contrast, its length usually exceeds 4 m.

If instance masks are available, the object mask can be used to estimate its orientation from a single image if the object footprint is rectangular. The mask is then transformed into world coordinates, after which an L-shaped fitting [29], [30] is performed, which estimates both the object dimensions, the object orientation, and its reference point.

D. Reference Point and Ground Point Estimation

After estimating the object orientations, the remaining detection variables can be calculated. Since no additional

Fig. 2. Overview of the reference point estimation algorithm. The reference edge or corner is estimated depending on the object orientation in image space $\hat{\alpha}$ indicated by the red arrow. In a), one of the rays defined by the projected bounding box is shifted by a set distance perpendicular to its world orientation ϑ (indicated by the light purple line) to estimate the reference point location (red points) and dimensions (yellow lines). In b), the bottom box edge is used directly to model the object, while in c), L-shaped fitting is used to estimate the reference point.

depth or shape information is available in the case of a standard object detector, we restrict our detection to reference points only, with the object dimension being an optional component. We distinguish two major cases for reference point detection based on the object orientation in image coordinates.

The first case occurs when the orientation angle is closer than a threshold of 7.5° , motivated by small-angle approximations, to the orientation of the horizontal or vertical image axes. In this case, the object moves towards or away from the camera or almost purely horizontally. Given the camera perspectives for roadside infrastructure, this effectively makes it impossible to estimate the dimension of the object along the depth axis of the camera. As a result, the width of the bounding box is transformed into world coordinates and is taken as either the width or length of the object, depending on its orientation. Meanwhile, the center of the bounding box's bottom edge is also transformed into world coordinates and used as the reference point encoded with x and y . The type p is set to front/back/left/right edge depending on the object orientation.

The other case occurs when the orientation angle does not satisfy the previously mentioned criteria. In this situation, the object moves along both image axes. To estimate a reference point, we exploit geometrical constraints. In particular, the vehicle point closest to both the ground and the camera must lie on the bottom box edge. By assuming an object width prior depending on the object class, a ground plane ray with the same orientation as the object and offset by the assumed width can be constructed and intersected with the bottom box edge to calculate the reference point. As can be seen in Fig. 2, since the offsetting of the ray by the width prior is done perpendicular to the object orientation (as indicated by the purple line), any error in the width assumption is scaled down by the dot product between vehicle orientation and

bounding box edge, making the reference point estimation more robust. Like the other case, p is set to front-right/front-left/back-right/back-left depending on the orientation. As the width is taken from a statistical prior and does not constitute an actual measurement, it is not included in the detection.

When instance masks are used, the reference point is obtained from the L-shaped fitting mentioned in the orientation estimation step. The reference point estimation for each case is shown in Fig. 2. For other object classes, such as bicycles and pedestrians, their footprint is reduced to their geometric center. This means that the bottom center of the box detection is used as the reference, regardless of the detector network.

E. Radar Target Processing and Clustering

Cost-effective automotive radar sensors are used to improve the reliability and redundancy of the processing pipeline. As the radar target measurements are provided in spherical coordinates, they are converted into Cartesian coordinates and then transformed into world coordinates. It should be noted that during this transformation, the radial velocity needs to be projected into the ground plane since the radial velocity vector is defined in the direction of the sensor, which in this case is mounted over the road and pitched down.

We can now use the transformed targets to find target clusters belonging to a single object. While a neural network object detector could also be trained for this purpose, no public infrastructure datasets providing automotive radar sensor data exist for training such networks. We, therefore, opted to use clustering by employing DBSCAN [31] since it does not require an underlying measurement model. To remove clutter measurements, targets with a radial velocity of < 0.1 m/s are filtered out. Then, the remaining targets are clustered using a distance metric based on the Euclidean distance between two points and their difference in radial velocity, allowing

us to distinguish between two close objects with different movement directions. Since pedestrians often only produce one target measurement due to their smaller radar cross-section, they cannot be clustered directly using DBSCAN since it requires at least 3 points in a cluster. Therefore, we buffer the two previous measurements and then perform DBSCAN using targets from three timestamps, allowing pedestrians to be clustered as well. Furthermore, this buffer-based clustering allows us to associate clusters between timestamps implicitly. The resulting associated target clusters can now be used for downstream detection and fusion tasks. If the clusters are to be sent out as detections, the convex hull of the cluster points can be taken as the vehicle’s footprint and converted to a reference point with corresponding length and width. Since the radar only measures the radial velocity component, the tangential velocity component has to be estimated. We realize this with the method described in [32]. The estimated tangential velocity component can then be combined with the other parameters to obtain object detections \mathbf{o}_j .

F. Sensor Fusion

If object detections are available from both camera sensors and radar sensors, both data sources can be fused. While there are different approaches for fusing heterogeneous sensor data, e.g., by using neural networks [33] or multi-object and track-to-track tracking algorithms [9], we cannot apply neural networks due to the absence of suitable datasets for supervised learning. Furthermore, no object tracking using kinematic models can be performed since the detections are sent to the digital twin, which fuses detections from various infrastructure sensors. Therefore, any model-based tracking would introduce a correlation between process and measurement noise. Due to these limitations, we perform a simple late fusion. As the radar and camera may have different update rates, we use camera frames to trigger the fusion. When the fusion module receives a camera detection, it tries associating it with any radar measurements received since the last camera frame was processed. The camera and radar detections are associated using the Hungarian algorithm, similar to the object bounding box association described in Subsection III-C. Instead of the DIoU, the Euclidean distance between the camera and radar detection reference points is used as the association score. Then, if camera and radar detections are associated, the detections can be merged in different ways. We decided to discard the radar detection and increase the detection confidence of the camera detection. Since the radar can measure velocities directly, the orientation of the radar detection may be more precise. Therefore, instead of discarding the radar measurement, the camera detection can also be updated using the radar detection, or the entire reference point estimation procedure can be repeated using the new value. If detections from either sensor cannot be associated, they are passed through the fusion module without modification. In the case of radar-only detections, the center of the target cluster is used as the reference point and treated as the object’s geometric center.

Furthermore, if the cluster contains a sufficient amount of targets, their convex hull in the ground plane can be used to estimate object dimensions.

IV. EVALUATION

In order to assess the applicability of the implemented detection approaches, we conducted an extensive real-world evaluation at our test site in Ulm-Lehr, Germany [11]. The following subsection describes our evaluation setup and methodology and provides our results.

A. Evaluation Setup

1) *Hardware Setup:* All recordings and evaluation tests were conducted at our test site in Ulm-Lehr. The test site consists of 6 light poles and one overhead gantry setup. Each pole and gantry are equipped with one to two intrinsically calibrated cameras. In addition, each light pole camera is also complemented by an automotive radar sensor capable of outputting spatial radar targets. Each camera has a resolution of 1920×1200 , a frame rate of 10 Hz, and is connected via 1Gbit Ethernet, while the radars have a fixed measurement rate of 15 Hz. Furthermore, some cameras are equipped with different lenses and thus have different fields of view, which enables us to assess the impact of the chosen camera view. The test site comprises 12 cameras and nine radar sensors mounted on poles. Each pole has an attached sensor processing unit (SPU), on which the detection pipeline is executed. The SPUs are equipped with NVIDIA RTX 3060 GPUs to achieve low latencies during neural network inference. For time synchronization with the server hosting the digital twin and accurate latency measurements, each pole is also equipped with a GPS receiver providing a GPS time source. For the processing pipeline itself, we use the YOLOv5s and YOLOv8s [7], [25] trained on the BDD100K dataset [8], while for the instance segmentation variant, the YOLOv8s-seg model was used with auto-labeled instance masks obtained from the BDD100K dataset boxes via Segment Anything [26]. The processed detections are sent to the digital twin via a 5G cellular test network.

2) *Environment:* The test site area is a small 3-way unsignalized intersection in an urban area containing sidewalks and bus stops. The sensors are extrinsically calibrated using our automated calibration method presented in [34] and [35]. Furthermore, a covered area is defined for each sensor such that captured areas on private properties are excluded, and the sensor’s detection range is limited to a range of 60 m.

3) *Evaluation Protocol:* Our evaluation covers multiple aspects of practical infrastructure perception. For the first scenario, both detections from the intersection and Collective Awareness Messages (CAMs) [36] from multiple intelligent vehicles passing through the intersection are recorded in the digital twin. The positions in the CAMs are obtained from precise localization systems and thus considered ground truth data. Then, all CAM messages are filtered to the covered areas of the infrastructure sensors. The detection with the closest timestamp is associated with the CAM for each CAM

and sensor measurement. Both the CAM and detection are then converted into a ground point rectangle. The CAM data is interpolated to the timestamp of the detection since time offsets between CAM and detection of only 50 ms can result in positional offsets of up to 0.5 m as the speed limit at the test site lies between 30 km/h and 40 km/h. Since the detection may not contain object dimensions, any missing dimensions are replaced with default values. We empirically chose 4.5 m as the default length and 1.8 m as the default width. The rectangle center distance between CAM and detection is used as the localization error. Using this metric, the orientation is implicitly included in the error metric since orientation errors during the conversion of reference points to ground rectangles get amplified due to the distance of the rectangle center from the reference point. In the final step, the detection is counted as valid if the distance between both rectangle centers is below 2.5 m. The detection rate η_{car} for the recorded scenario can be measured by comparing the number of valid associated CAMs to the total number of CAMs in the sensor coverage area. In addition to the detection rate and average localization error $\delta_{p,m}$, the average absolute orientation errors $|\delta_{\theta,m}|$ and absolute average dimension errors $|\delta_{d,m}|$ are reported for the camera-only evaluation, where only lengths and widths from real measurements are considered, and default values are discarded. To illustrate the influence of the camera configuration, we provide the focal length f of each camera.

In the second scenario, multiple sequences are coarsely annotated in 1-second intervals, where all objects entering and exiting the sensor coverage area are marked. Using these labels, detection rates for classes without ground truth information can be approximated, which is especially important for vulnerable road users such as pedestrians and cyclists. Therefore, we measure the detection rates η_{car} , η_{ped} , and η_{bike} .

For the third scenario, the latency from recording camera images to receiving detections at the digital twin is measured. It should be noted that the perception pipeline, while implemented in C++ and Python and built on the ROS2 framework, should still be considered prototypical, as the hardware configuration and software stack are only partially optimized towards lower detection latencies. Also, the latencies were only measured with the YOLOv5 model due to its lower computational complexity. Overall, apart from sequence “22_snow”, each presented sequence from all three scenarios is sourced from different camera views of the same recording containing image data, digital twin inputs, and vehicle CAMs.

B. Evaluation Results and Discussion

1) *Localization Performance*: The evaluation results for the first scenario using vehicle ground truth locations are shown in Table I. It should be noted that the quality of the sensor calibration also limits the quality of the reference point estimation. As we used our method described in [34], the additional error added through the reference point estimation process is in a similar range as the original calibration error. We also notice a small benefit of fusing radar data,

TABLE I
EVALUATION RESULTS FROM REAL-WORLD SEQUENCES.

	Seq. ID	01	21	22	41	51
	f	2175	815	2185	1065	1074
YOLOv5	η_{car} [%]	99.3	81.1	99.7	95.7	99.5
	η_{car} (fused)	-	94.5	99.7	97.5	-
	$\delta_{p,m}$ [m]	0.52	0.70	0.29	0.61	0.32
	$\delta_{p,m}$ (fused)	-	0.70	0.29	0.62	-
	$ \delta_{d,m} $ [m]	0.3	0.6	0.2	0.6	1.0
	$ \delta_{\theta,m} $ [°]	13.6	4.6	0.6	13.7	12.4
YOLOv8	η_{car} [%]	99.5	82.2	99.6	98.2	94.4
	η_{car} (fused)	-	91.8	99.6	98.8	-
	$\delta_{p,m}$ [m]	0.51	0.67	0.30	0.59	0.32
	$\delta_{p,m}$ (fused)	-	0.67	0.30	0.56	-
	$ \delta_{d,m} $ [m]	0.4	0.7	0.2	0.6	1.0
	$ \delta_{\theta,m} $ [°]	10.2	6.6	2.2	11.8	13.0
YOLOv8s-seg	η_{car} [%]	98.2	63.0	97.1	82.0	92.2
	η_{car} (fused)	-	74.6	98.8	85.3	-
	$\delta_{p,m}$ [m]	0.51	1.00	0.81	0.77	0.69
	$\delta_{p,m}$ (fused)	-	0.96	0.82	0.80	-
	$ \delta_{d,m} $ [m]	0.8	1.2	0.5	0.8	0.8
	$ \delta_{\theta,m} $ [°]	12.6	4.0	0.8	10.1	11.6

especially on sequence 21, which uses a wide-angle lens and thus has a lower camera detection rate when compared to the other sensors, especially the sensor used for sequence 22, which uses a tele lens. Furthermore, the localization accuracy of the fused case is only slightly impacted by the radar fusion since we use radar data only if no matching camera detection is available, and the localization accuracy of a radar detection roughly matches the camera’s performance. The camera pose can explain the large differences between average errors. While the cameras in sequences 22 and 42 overlook an almost straight stretch of road, sequences 01, 41, and 51 capture the center of the intersection and parts of a parking lot next to the road. Due to the orientation smoothing by Eq. 1, the estimated orientation will lag behind the true orientation in areas where vehicles are turning. It should be noted that the localization and dimension errors of the YOLOv8-seg evaluation are higher than the rest. This can be partially attributed to the higher amount of dimension measurements from the instance masks and the influence of an incorrect dimension estimation on the detection box center location.

2) *Class-Specific Detection Rate*: The second scenario evaluation results presented in Table II show a significant performance benefit when using a camera-radar setup. While the detection rate improvements of vehicles are limited by the already high detection rate of a camera-only pipeline, pedestrians and especially cyclists’ detection rates are significantly improved. When comparing with other works, such as [5] and [6], we achieve comparable detection performance while not relying on infrastructure-specific datasets for training the detectors. We can also notice an improvement in the

TABLE II

DETECTION RATE EVALUATION ON ANNOTATED TEST SEQUENCES.

	Seq. ID	11	12	21	22	41	22_snow
	f	1074	1075	815	2185	1065	2185
YOLOv5	η_{car}	100.0	99.6	99.1	100.0	90.6	94.9
	$\eta_{\text{car,fused}}$	100.0	100.0	99.1	100.0	96.2	97.2
	η_{ped}	93.7	80.2	87.6	99.9	94.9	83.1
	$\eta_{\text{ped,fused}}$	96.8	99.5	95.5	99.9	96.7	98.1
	η_{bike}	10.5	39.7	26.8	50.6	70.5	31.6
	$\eta_{\text{bike,fused}}$	31.7	71.0	64.2	67.0	85.8	76.7
YOLOv8	η_{car}	100.0	99.6	96.2	100.0	88.7	99.4
	$\eta_{\text{car,fused}}$	100.0	99.8	96.2	100.0	95.1	99.9
	η_{ped}	88.9	83.7	84.4	99.5	91.7	85.8
	$\eta_{\text{ped,fused}}$	93.6	94.2	92.3	99.9	95.2	98.2
	η_{bike}	38.8	76.9	72.1	88.1	96.2	47.4
	$\eta_{\text{bike,fused}}$	56.2	84.2	84.3	90.5	97.0	77.9
YOLOv8s-seg	η_{car}	100.0	100.0	97.5	100.0	89.6	94.9
	$\eta_{\text{car,fused}}$	100.0	100.0	97.8	100.0	93.8	99.0
	η_{ped}	85.3	79.6	83.7	99.8	89.9	81.2
	$\eta_{\text{ped,fused}}$	93.5	99.3	94.4	99.9	95.5	97.9
	η_{bike}	41.7	80.9	50.1	82.8	94.8	39.7
	$\eta_{\text{bike,fused}}$	67.6	84.2	76.9	86.8	96.3	78.0

generalization ability of the YOLOv8 models since their cyclist detection rates are much higher than YOLOv5. At the same time, the other classes perform similarly or even slightly worse. Another positive aspect of YOLO’s generalization and domain adaptation ability is the use of a large, generic automated driving dataset like BDD100K for training, which eliminates the need to label specific infrastructure sensor data and thus simplifies the development of such processing pipelines. To check the robustness of our pipeline in adverse weather conditions, we recorded and annotated a new sequence on camera 22 during dusk and snowstorms, which creates a challenging environment for object detection. While cars and pedestrians could still be reliably detected with camera data only, cyclist detection suffers from snowy, low-light conditions. However, it achieves similar performance to the base, good weather scenario when fused with radar data. An example of this scene is shown in Fig. 3.

3) *Latency and Real-World Use:* For the third scenario, the latency histograms for our setup are visualized in Fig. 4. We distinguish between single-camera and two-camera latencies since some of our roadside units have two cameras connected to the same processing unit using a shared 1Gbit Ethernet link, thus increasing image transmission latency. We measure the latency as the time between the beginning of the image frame exposure and the arrival of the processed detections at the digital twin. Thus, it consists of the exposure time, transmission time to the processing unit, pipeline runtime, and cellular network transmission latency to the digital twin server. Considering the results of our test site, we achieve a complete system latency below our update rate of 100 ms and lower than the replanning time of both

Fig. 3. Example of an adversarial scene contained in “22_snow”. Camera detections are drawn as boxes, while measured target clusters are shown in cyan, and the estimated reference point is shown in purple. The measured or estimated radial velocities, object orientations, and object dimensions are drawn as pink, green, and beige lines, respectively.

Fig. 4. Latency distribution of the box detector pipeline, measured between triggering the camera and receiving the object data at the digital twin, e.g., around 11 % of incoming detections in the single-camera pipeline have a latency between 65 ms and 67 ms. 0.43 % of incoming detections were discarded due to the latency exceeding 120 ms. Due to the buffering of radar clusters during fusion and late fusion approach, the fusion module only adds around 7 ms of latency on average.

cooperative planners used for maneuver tests. It should be noted that a large part of the latency is caused by the image transmission time from the camera to the processing unit, adding at least 30 ms. Therefore, the overall system latency can be lowered by using better camera communication links.

Overall, the results show that our pipeline meets desirable performance requirements for cooperative maneuver planning, e.g., the methods shown in [37] and [38]. In this specific case, we expect latencies lower than the replanning time to obtain an up-to-date environment model during each replanning step as well as localization accuracies below 1 m since the performance of the cooperative planner is limited by its scene prediction accuracy. These requirements are satisfied. As a last performance indicator, a qualitative proof of our proposed method’s use for cooperative maneuvers is shown in [39], where our test site setup provided object data to perform a cooperative three-way intersection crossing scenario with three automated vehicles.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented an efficient object detection method for infrastructure cameras that only requires object bounding boxes, provides reference points, and does not rely on infrastructure datasets for model training. In addition, we also designed a radar data processing pipeline that does not rely on learning-based approaches, such as neural networks, as well as simple fusion strategies for combining camera and radar object detection. In order to show the usability of our pipeline, we conducted an extensive evaluation of our approaches on real sequences from a test site used for cooperative maneuver testing by considering the localization accuracy, detection rate, and latency of our pipeline while also comparing it to an instance mask-based approach.

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